

MATHEMATICAL CONCEPT OF ANGULAR DIMENSIONS

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Abstract

In this work, I introduce a new mathematical concept of angular dimensions, which may offer a deeper understanding of the fabric of space and time. Traditionally, the angle has not been regarded as a quantity with dimensional characteristics; instead, it has been treated as a dimensionless number. However, within the mathematical framework I propose, the angle inherently possesses a fundamental vector dimensional property.

After establishing the concept of angular dimensions, I will utilize only a subset of these possible dimensions to construct a mathematical framework for space and time. As the theory of angular dimensions unfolds, new insights into the nature of space and time will emerge.

Furthermore, the mathematical concept of angular dimensions reveals the existence of multiple dimensions and their quantization, offering an alternative mathematical foundation for quantum physics. This concept also opens new avenues for mathematical research, as our approach represents just one among infinitely many possible configurations of angular dimensions for describing space-time. Exploring other arrangements could lead to a vast and promising field of mathematical inquiry.

Keywords: Mathematical Physics (math-ph); Quantum Cosmology (gr-qc); Quantum Physics (quant-ph); Space-time; Speed of light.

1. Introduction

Until now, the acceptance of the dimensional nature of angles has been a subject of controversy [1]. In this work, I explore the origins of this controversy through the new perspective introduced by the theory of angular dimensions. I conclude that we have long confused the radius of a circumference with the conversion factor between angle and arc length (or space) in that circumference. This confusion has led to several mistakes.

The most significant mistake has been treating angles as dimensionless entities, which has prevented us from considering the possible existence of an angular universe where angles possess a fundamental vector-dimensional property. Another mistake has been the establishment of formulae such as the arc length of a circumference, $L = \alpha R$, or the area of a circle, $A = \pi R^2$, which are only considered valid when the angle is measured in radians and the radius in meters. However, we know that mathematical and physical equations must hold true regardless of the units used to measure the different quantities involved. The key requirement is that the equations must be dimensionally consistent.

This realization suggests the existence of an illogical presumption. However, because these formulae yield correct numerical results only when angles are expressed in radians and the radius in meters, we fail to recognize that they are dimensionally incorrect. This mistake becomes even more significant when these formulae are applied in the calculation of complex physical quantities, such as for instance the magnetic moment of a rotating electric charge, where we use the formula $\mu = I A$. The dimensional inconsistency prevents us from understanding the true origin of the intrinsic magnetic moment of the electron.

Several theories consider the multidimensional nature of space-time, including String Theory [2][3], General Relativity [4], Loop Quantum Gravity [5], M Theory [6], among others. Both Loop Quantum Gravity and String Theory address the quantization of space and time at extremely small scales. However, these theories regard space and time as primary entities in the universe, rather than deriving them mathematically from more fundamental constructs.

In contrast, our Angular Dimensions Theory integrates both multidimensionality and the quantization of space and time within a mathematical framework in which space and time emerge as derived magnitudes from a more fundamental quantity: the angle. We will see that the speed of light can be understood as a mathematical relationship between angular dimensions, establishing a structured connection among them.

2. Universe of angular dimensions

My proposition is based on three fundamental ideas. The first is that there is no logical contradiction in giving the concept of angle a vector dimensional character. The second is that I consider the mathematical existence of infinite independent angular dimensions α_i ($i = 1, 2, 3 \dots \infty$). The concept of independence means that it holds true,

$$\alpha_i \cdot \alpha_j = 0; \text{ if } i \neq j; \quad \alpha_i \cdot \alpha_i = (\alpha_i)^2. \quad (1)$$

Where the point “•” indicate scalar product.

The value of an angle in each angular dimension ranges from 0 rd to $2\pi\text{ rd}$ if the angle is measured in the positive direction or from 0 rd to $-2\pi\text{ rd}$ if the angle is measured in the negative direction. The angle in each angular dimension must be measured relative to a reference or origin, where the angle is defined as zero. I could designate it as X_i for the angular dimension α_i ($i = 1,2,3 \dots \infty$).

The third is that what I perceive as space and time is manifestations of different logical-mathematical organization and structures of these infinite angular dimensions.

These infinite angular dimensions can be organized in different ways according to different criteria. These different organizations can be considered as possible angular mathematical universes.

The first possible organization is achieved by establishing the criterion that an angular dimension has only one other angular dimension associated with it and vice versa. For example, angular dimension 1 has 2 associated with it and vice versa, 3 has 4 associated with it and vice versa... I could say that each angular dimension has only one other associated with it. With this consideration I would have infinite angular dimensions put together into independent angular pairs. I could say that I would have infinite independent two-dimensional angular universes because no pair could share any angular dimension with another pair.

The second organization is achieved by establishing the criterion that two angular dimensions are associated only with a third angular dimension, but that third can be associated with multiple pairs of angular dimensions different from the previous ones. With this second criterion the infinite angular dimensions are grouped into triplets, but not independent ones since all the triplets can share their angular dimensions with other different triplets. For example, in the triplet (1,2,3) 1 and 2 are associated only with 3, 2 and 3 are associated only with 1, 1 and 3 are associated only with 2. Therefore, no triplet will exist in which 1 and 2 are associated with, for example, 4. However, 3 can be part of the triplet (3,4,7) or (3,8,5), etc. That is, 3 can be associated not only with 1 and 2, but also with 4 and 7 or 8 and 5, but 4 and 7 are associated only with 3, and 8 and 5 are associated only with 3. This second organization is the most interesting to explain our physical space and time.

According to this second criterion, the organizations of infinite triplets of angular dimensions would be as shown in the attached Illustration 1, where each vertical set of three angular dimensions constitutes a triplet.

5	1	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	4	10	10...
6	2	4	4	4	8	8	8	9	9	9	8	11	4...
7	3	5	6	7	6	7	5	7	5	6	9	12	13...

Illustration 1: To see how the following table of triplets is built according to our criteria, I will put the obtaining of the first ones. If I start from the first triplet (1,2,3) and I want to build a second triplet, for example (1,4,?) in the interrogation I cannot put the angular dimension 2 because 1 and 2 define only 3 but not 4. Likewise, I cannot put the angular dimension 3 because 1 and 3 define only 2. Thus, the next angular dimension must be different from 1, 2, 3, and 4, making it 5. Then, following the same reasoning if I consider the new triplet (2,4,?) in the interrogation I will have to put the new angular dimension 6 and so on. This organization would continue to infinity.

In the first twelve triplets formed exclusively with the angular dimensions 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9, I can choose three triplets that do not have common angular dimensions.

For example, the triplets (1,2,3), (5,6,7) and (4,8,9). Because they do not have common angular dimension I can be sure that any angular direction α_{123} in triplet (1,2,3), any angular direction α_{489} in triplet (4,8,9) and any angular direction α_{567} in triplet (5,6,7) will be independent.

The first I am going to do is establish a criterion of quantization in triplets (1,2,3) and (4,8,9). In the triplet (1,2,3) consider angular quanta in each of the angular dimensions,

$$|\tilde{\alpha}_i| = \frac{2\pi}{N_i} \quad (i = 1,2,3). \quad (2)$$

Where each N_i can be any integer from 1 to infinity ($N_i = 1,2,3, \dots \infty$).

Also in the triplet (4,8,9) I consider angular quanta in each of the angular dimensions

$$|\tilde{\alpha}_j| = \frac{2\pi}{N_j} \quad (j = 4,8,9), \quad (3)$$

where each N_j can be any integer from 1 to infinity ($N_j = 1,2,3, \dots \infty$). The values that adopt N_i or N_j can be equal or different.

This structure of angular quanta has a series of quantum rotations that I will designate by n . The quantum rotation in angular dimension α_i means that the reference X_i experience a quantum rotation $\tilde{\alpha}_i$. Quantum rotation is considered positive when it follows the positive direction of rotation and negative when it follows the negative direction. These quantum rotations are synchronized in any angular dimension $\tilde{\alpha}_i$ ($i = 1,2,3$) and $\tilde{\alpha}_j$ ($j = 4,8,9$). Synchronization means that when a quantum rotation takes place in one angular dimension, it also occurs in the other angular dimensions. Therefore, they are synchronized in any angular direction $\tilde{\alpha}_{123}$ in triplet (1,2,3) and in any angular direction $\tilde{\alpha}_{489}$ in triplet (4,8,9).

After n quantum rotations the angular displacements of references X_i in triplet (1,2,3) will have components $\alpha_i = n \tilde{\alpha}_i$ ($i = 1,2,3$) ($n = 1,2,3 \dots$) and the angular displacements of references X_j in triplet (4,8,9) will have components $\alpha_j = n \tilde{\alpha}_j$ ($j = 4,8,9$) ($n = 1,2,3 \dots$). I can define unitary angular vectors $\tilde{\alpha}_{i(\text{unitary})}$ and $\tilde{\alpha}_{j(\text{unitary})}$. They would be unitary and with the positive direction of rotation of the angular directions α_i and α_j respectively. Then, I can conclude that:

$$\tilde{\alpha}_i = \pm |\tilde{\alpha}_i| \tilde{\alpha}_{i(\text{unitary})} \quad (i = 1,2,3), \quad (4)$$

And

$$\tilde{\alpha}_j = \pm |\tilde{\alpha}_j| \tilde{\alpha}_{j(\text{unitary})} \quad (j = 4,8,9), \quad (5)$$

respectively.

Based on the previous reasoning, I can see that I am dealing with angular magnitudes, where each angular dimension can be assigned a module and a positive and negative angular direction. Therefore, I can use vector algebra in angular dimensions.

The angular quanta $\tilde{\alpha}_i$ ($i = 1,2,3$) and $\tilde{\alpha}_j$ ($j = 4,8,9$) define the quantum of angular vector $\tilde{\alpha}_{123}$,

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{123} = \tilde{\alpha}_1 + \tilde{\alpha}_2 + \tilde{\alpha}_3, \quad (6)$$

and the quantum of angular vector $\tilde{\alpha}_{489}$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{489} = \tilde{\alpha}_4 + \tilde{\alpha}_8 + \tilde{\alpha}_9, \quad (7)$$

respectively. These quanta of angular vectors define an angular direction in the triplets (1,2,3) and (4,8,9), respectively. The quantization of these vectors $\tilde{\alpha}_{123}$ and $\tilde{\alpha}_{489}$, is determined by the following equations:

$$|\tilde{\alpha}_{123}| = \frac{2\pi}{N_{123}}, \quad (8)$$

And

$$|\tilde{\alpha}_{489}| = \frac{2\pi}{N_{489}}, \quad (9)$$

respectively. Where N_{123} and N_{489} are mathematical functions of N_i ($i = 1,2,3$) and N_j ($j = 4,8,9$) respectively.

I can establish also the existence of a reference $X_{123} \leftrightarrow (X_1, X_2, X_3)$ as origin of angles α_{123} in triplet (1,2,3) and a reference $X_{489} \leftrightarrow (X_4, X_8, X_9)$ as origin of angles α_{489} in triplet (4,8,9).

Recall that in each triplet (1,2,3) and (4,8,9) the angular dimensions are mutually independent.

Thus, I can establish that the following equations hold true in the triplet (1,2,3):

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{123}^2 = \tilde{\alpha}_1^2 + \tilde{\alpha}_2^2 + \tilde{\alpha}_3^2, \quad (10)$$

$$|\tilde{\alpha}_{123}|^2 = |\tilde{\alpha}_1|^2 + |\tilde{\alpha}_2|^2 + |\tilde{\alpha}_3|^2 = \left(\frac{2\pi}{N_{123}}\right)^2, \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{123} = \pm |\tilde{\alpha}_{123} | \tilde{\alpha}_{123(\text{unitary})}, \quad (12)$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{N_{123}}\right)^2 = \sum_{i=1,2,3} \left(\frac{1}{N_i}\right)^2. \quad (13)$$

Likewise, in the triplet (4,8,9) are verified identical equations from (10) to (13) but with the index number 4,8,9 instead of 1,2,3 respectively.

According to eqs.(2) to (13) in triplet (1,2,3) and the corresponding in triplet (4,8,9) there are many quantum angular directions in the triplets (1,2,3) and (4,8,9) depending on the particular values of de $\tilde{\alpha}_i$ ($i = 1,2,3$) and $\tilde{\alpha}_j$ ($j = 4,8,9$) respectively.

The triplet (1,2,3) and triplet (4,8,9) do not have any angular dimensions in common. Therefore, any quantum of angular direction $\tilde{\alpha}_{489}$ will be independent to any quantum of angular direction $\tilde{\alpha}_{123}$,

$$\tilde{\alpha}_1 \tilde{\alpha}_4 + \tilde{\alpha}_2 \tilde{\alpha}_8 + \tilde{\alpha}_3 \tilde{\alpha}_9 = 0. \quad (14)$$

After n quantum rotations, the following equations hold for the triplet (1,2,3):

$$\alpha_i = n \tilde{\alpha}_i \rightarrow \alpha_i = \pm n |\tilde{\alpha}_i | \tilde{\alpha}_{i(\text{unitary})} \quad (15)$$

$$(i = 1,2,3)(n = 1,2,3 \dots),$$

$$\alpha_{123} = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = n \tilde{\alpha}_1 + n \tilde{\alpha}_2 + n \tilde{\alpha}_3 = n \tilde{\alpha}_{123}, \quad (16)$$

$$|\alpha_{123}| = n |\tilde{\alpha}_{123} | (n = 1,2,3 \dots). \quad (17)$$

In the triplet (4,8,9) will obtain the same equations from (15) to (17) but with the index number 4,8,9 instead of 1,2,3 respectively.

In order to define velocities that relate the quantum of angular vectors $\tilde{\alpha}_{123}$ with the quantum of angular vectors $\tilde{\alpha}_{489}$ I will consider the triplet (1,2,3) as spatial and the triplet (4,8,9) as temporal. Then, I will consider the angular vectors $\tilde{\alpha}_{123}$ as spatial and angular vectors $\tilde{\alpha}_{489}$ as temporal. I can define a dimensionless angular velocity $\tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489}$ that relate any quantum of spatial angular component $\tilde{\alpha}_i$ ($i = 1,2,3$) with any quantum of temporal angular ones $\tilde{\alpha}_j$ ($j = 4,8,9$) and the module of any quantum of spatial angular vector $|\tilde{\alpha}_{123}|$ with the module of any quantum of temporal angular vector $|\tilde{\alpha}_{489}|$.

$$\tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489} = \frac{|\tilde{\alpha}_i|}{|\tilde{\alpha}_j|} = \frac{N_j}{N_i}; (i = 1,2,3)(j = 4,8,9), \quad (18)$$

the eq. (18) means that the relation of the modulus of any quantum of spatial angular component $|\tilde{\alpha}_i|$ ($i = 1,2,3$) with the modulus of any quantum of temporal angular component $|\tilde{\alpha}_j|$ ($j = 4,8,9$) will be always the dimensionless angular velocity $\tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489}$.

$$\tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489} = \frac{|\tilde{\alpha}_{123}|}{|\tilde{\alpha}_{489}|} = \frac{N_{489}}{N_{123}}, \quad (19)$$

the eq. (19) means that the relation of the modulus of any quantum of spatial angular vector $|\tilde{\alpha}_{123}|$, with the modulus of any quantum of temporal angular vector $|\tilde{\alpha}_{489}|$, will be also the dimensionless angular velocity $\tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489}$.

If I multiply and divide by n the eqs. (18)(19) according to eqs. (15)(17) in triplet (1,2,3) and their equivalents in triplet (4,8,9) it is verified:

$$\tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489} = \frac{|\alpha_i|}{|\alpha_j|}; (i = 1,2,3)(j = 4,8,9), \quad (20)$$

$$\tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489} = \frac{|\alpha_{123}|}{|\alpha_{489}|}. \quad (21)$$

If I consider a certain angular direction α_{123} in the triplet (1,2,3) defined by some components $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3)$ I find that, when is established the relationships defined in the eqs.(20)(21), the dimensionless angular speed relates an angular direction α_{123} in triplet (1,2,3) to 6 different angular directions α_{489} in the triplet (4,8,9),

$$|\alpha_{123}| = \sqrt{(\alpha_1)^2 + (\alpha_2)^2 + (\alpha_3)^2} \quad (22)$$

$$= \tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123} \sqrt{(\alpha_{j=4,8,9})^2 + (\alpha_{k=4,8,9})^2 + (\alpha_{l=4,8,9})^2};$$

$$(j \neq k \neq l).$$

I see that for a given spatial direction α_{123} there is not a single temporal direction α_{489} since the angular direction 1 can be associated with the 4 in the triplet (1,4,5), or with the 8 in the triplet (1,8,6) or with the 9 in the triplet (1,9,7). The same can be said for the angular direction 2 since it can be associated with the 4 in the triplet (2,4,6), or with the 8 in the triplet (2,8,7) or with the 9 in the triplet (2,9,5). Likewise, the angular direction 3 can be associated with the 4 in the triplet (3,4,7), or with the 8 in the triplet (3,8,5) or with the 9 in the triplet (3,9,6).

According to eq. (22) a spatial angular direction α_{123} can be associated with temporal angular directions α_{489} in six different ways.

$$(1,2,3) \rightarrow \begin{cases} \{4,8,9 \text{ triplet } (1,4,5) \text{ triplet } (2,8,7) \text{ triplet } (3,9,6) \\ 4,9,8 \text{ triplet } (1,4,5) \text{ triplet } (2,9,5) \text{ triplet } (3,8,5) \\ 8,9,4 \text{ triplet } (1,8,6) \text{ triplet } (2,9,5) \text{ triplet } (3,4,7) \\ 8,4,9 \text{ triplet } (1,8,6) \text{ triplet } (2,4,6) \text{ triplet } (3,9,6) \\ 9,8,4 \text{ triplet } (1,9,7) \text{ triplet } (2,8,7) \text{ triplet } (3,4,7) \\ 9,4,8 \text{ triplet } (1,9,7) \text{ triplet } (2,4,6) \text{ triplet } (3,8,5) \end{cases}$$

I can then reason that a given temporal angular direction α_{489} can be associated with spatial angular directions (1,2,3) in six different ways.

Therefore, in our angular universe two points separated by a spatial angular distance $|\alpha_{123}|$ are necessarily separated by a temporal angular distance $|\alpha_{489}| = \frac{|\alpha_{123}|}{\tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123}}$. Then, it would be wrong to assign the same instant of time to two different points in space.

If I consider the triplet (4,8,9) as spatial and the triplet (1,2,3) as temporal, everything would be symmetrical with a dimensionless angular speed $\tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489} = \frac{|\tilde{\alpha}_{489}|}{|\tilde{\alpha}_{123}|} = \frac{N_{123}}{N_{489}}$, verifying:

$$\tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123} \tilde{c}_{triplet123}^{triplet489} = 1. \quad (23)$$

The dimensionless angular speed $\tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123}$ is related to linear speed of light $c_{triplet489}^{triplet123} = 299.792,458 \left(\frac{m}{s}\right)$ used in our physical theories. It is enough to introduce some dimensional constants that transform the angles either to space or time. I will designate these constants as $R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd}\right)$ and $R_{angle}^{time} \left(\frac{s}{rd}\right)$.

With $R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd}\right)$ I change angles(rd) to space(m),

$$\tilde{e}_{123}(m) = R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd}\right) \tilde{\alpha}_{123}(rd). \quad (24)$$

Then $\tilde{e}_{123}(m)$ is the quantum of linear space vector that correspond to the quantum of spatial angular vector $\tilde{\alpha}_{123}(rd)$.

With $R_{angle}^{time} \left(\frac{s}{rd}\right)$ I change angles(rd) to time(s),

$$\tilde{t}_{489}(s) = R_{angle}^{time} \left(\frac{s}{rd}\right) \tilde{\alpha}_{489}(rd). \quad (25)$$

Then $\tilde{t}_{489}(s)$ is the quantum of linear temporal vector that correspond to the quantum of temporal angular vector $\tilde{\alpha}_{489}(rd)$. If I multiply the eqs. (24)(25) by the number of quantum rotation n I obtain the total space $e_{123}(m)$ and time $t_{489}(s)$ vectors,

$$e_{123}(m) = R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd}\right) n \tilde{\alpha}_{123}(rd) = n \tilde{e}_{123}, \quad (26)$$

$$t_{489}(s) = R_{angle}^{time} \left(\frac{s}{rd}\right) n \tilde{\alpha}_{489}(rd) = n \tilde{t}_{489}. \quad (27)$$

I see then that both time and space are quantized.

Consequently, taking into account the eq. (19) I can obtain the relationship between the linear speed of light $c_{triplet489}^{triplet123} \left(\frac{m}{s}\right)$ and the angular speed $\tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123}$ with the following formula:

$$c_{triplet489}^{triplet123} \left(\frac{m}{s}\right) = \frac{|\tilde{e}_{123}|(m)}{|\tilde{t}_{489}|(s)} = \frac{R_{angle}^{space} |\tilde{\alpha}_{123}|}{R_{angle}^{time} |\tilde{\alpha}_{489}|} = R_{time}^{space} \tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123}. \quad (28)$$

Where,

$$R_{time}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{s} \right) = \frac{R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd} \right)}{R_{angle}^{time} \left(\frac{s}{rd} \right)} = \text{constant.} \quad (29)$$

R_{angle}^{space} can vary but then R_{angle}^{time} varies proportionally keeping R_{time}^{space} constant.

However, I can use only one of them, for example $R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd} \right)$. This means that I use the meter to measure both space and time. In this case, the only speed of light that I will use will be the dimensionless angular velocity $\tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123}$,

$$\frac{|\tilde{e}_{123}|(m)}{|\tilde{e}_{489}|(m)} = \frac{R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd} \right) |\tilde{\alpha}_{123}|(rd)}{R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd} \right) |\tilde{\alpha}_{489}|(rd)} = \tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123}. \quad (30)$$

If I multiply and divide the eq.(28) by the number of quantum rotations n and I take into account the eqs. (26)(27), the following equation holds:

$$c_{triplet489}^{triplet123} = \frac{|e_{123}|}{|t_{489}|} = \frac{R_{angle}^{space} |\alpha_{123}|}{R_{angle}^{time} |\alpha_{489}|} = R_{time}^{space} \tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123}. \quad (31)$$

With one of the multiple dimensionless angular velocities $\tilde{c}_{triplet489}^{triplet123}$ the structure of the space and time can be defined.

I must consider that R_{angle}^{space} is a conversion factor from angle units to space units, it is not a distance(m) or radius(m) in what I perceive as space. I think it is convenient to do a clarification because one of the reasons that has led to considering angles as dimensionless entities has been to accept that in a circumference the conversion factor from angle (rd) to arc (m) covered by that angle on the circumference is the radius (m). When posing the equations of a circumference of radius R, I have confused two different concepts. One is the conversion factor R_{angle}^{space} from angle to space on the circumference and another is the distance R from the center of the circumference to the points of the circumference. They are two different concepts that are measured with different units, but the number is the same if the radian is used as unit of measurement for angles and meters for distances. If I use for example another unit of measurement for angles, such as cycle, the conversion factor $R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{cycle} \right)$ would be a different number than one of radius R(m).

The number π come from the factor of transformation between $R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{cycle} \right)$ and $R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd} \right)$,

$$R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{cycle} \right) = R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd} \right) 2\pi \frac{rd}{cycle}. \quad (32)$$

This reasoning about the true concept of the angle to distance conversion factor $R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd} \right)$ can shed light on the controversy raised in the work of Peter J. Mohr and others [1]

Nevertheless, the confusion of the angle to space conversion introduce furthermore errors in mathematical physics formulae. I can consider for instance the calculus of area A of a circle and the calculus of the magnetic moment μ of a rotating charge q that is defined by the expression $\mu = I A$. Where I is the intensity of the electric current and A the area of the circuit where the electric current is defined. Without considering the angular dimensions and the dimensional character of the angles today it is considered that the area of a circle is $A = \pi (R^{space})^2$ which is not dimensionally correct since it forgets the dimensional character of the angle πrd . The true formula for the area of a circle must be calculated as:

$$A(m^2) = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{2} R^{space} R_{angle}^{space} d\alpha = \pi(rd) R^{space}(m) R_{angle}^{space} \left(\frac{m}{rd} \right) \quad (33)$$

Then we can calculate the magnetic moment of the electric charge q as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu = I A &= \frac{q}{T} \pi R^{space} R_{angle}^{space} = \frac{q \pi R^{space} R_{angle}^{space}}{\frac{2\pi R_{angle}^{space}}{v}} = \\ &= \frac{q v R^{space}}{2} = \frac{q v m_q R^{space}}{2 m_q} = \frac{q}{2 m_q} L \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

With these considerations, I will be able to derive a comprehensible expression for the origin of the intrinsic magnetic moment of the electron in a future work, where I will obtain the equation of the electron based on the theory of angular dimensions.

3. Conclusions

Having conceptually confused the angle to space conversion factor has not only led us to consider angles as dimensionless entities but also to make mistakes in certain physical formulas where when rotations appear, this conversion factor must necessarily be taken into account.

I believe that the concepts of space and time introduced in this work provide an alternative explanation for experimental observations—one that remains consistent with

current theories while offering a deeper insight into the fundamental principles governing space-time.

The mathematical framework developed here opens new pathways for exploring the universe from a fresh perspective and investigating the subatomic realm using novel mathematical tools.

From a mathematical standpoint, this theory introduces a vast research field centered on the universe of infinite angular dimensions, examining their potential structures and interrelations.

Future work will focus on developing a model for the photon based on the theory of angular dimensions.

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